

Late Afternoon Program and Letter Recognition Skills of Grade One Learners

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Abstract. This study sought to determine the effect of the late afternoon program and letter recognition skills on grade one learners. Eventually, it also aims to assess the magnitude of the impact of the action initiated by the researcher on the academic performance of the research subjects. This study uses the quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design was good when the researcher had access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are an intact group of learners. This study will be conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 60 grade one learners – 28 are from section A, which will be the controlled group, and 32 are from section B, which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study uses the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of sections A and B are involved as study subjects. Since it is pandemic time, the experiment will be conducted based on the mechanics of the Distant Learning Program. This study revealed that the utilization of the late afternoon program has increased the letter recognition skills of grade one learners. It also showed a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. late afternoon program
2. letter recognition skills
3. decode words
4. personal development

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1. Introduction

A late afternoon program (LAP) for students typically offers a mix of academic support, extracurricular activities, and opportunities for personal development. It aims to provide students with a structured environment during the crucial hours after regular school hours, fostering educational enrichment and social engagement. Late afternoon or after-school programs are structured activities and services offered to students outside of regular school hours, typically in the late afternoon or early evening. These programs serve various purposes, including academic support, extracurricular enrichment, and personal development. They aim to provide students with a safe and constructive environment when they are not in school, offering opportunities for learning, growth, and engagement (2019). As a student participating in a late afternoon program, you can benefit in several ways, including academic support, personal development, socialization, and engagement in enriching activities. Late afternoon programs often

include extracurricular activities such as arts, music, sports, and STEM, providing opportunities for students to explore their interests and talents (Eccles Gootman, 2021). After-school programs offer a safe and structured environment for students during the hours when juvenile crime and risky behaviors are more likely to occur (Mahoney et al., 2019). These programs often include opportunities for physical activity, which contributes to improved physical health and reduced risk of obesity among children and adolescents (Beets et al., 2020). Letter recognition skills are foundational for early literacy development in grade-one students. These skills involved identifying and differentiating between letters of the alphabet, which is crucial for reading and writing. Grade-one students typically begin by learning to recognize uppercase and lowercase letters individually. They gradually progress to identifying letters in various fonts and sizes (National Early Literacy Panel, 2021). As students develop letter recognition skills, they also learn the sounds associated with each letter, essential for decoding words and beginning reading (National Reading Panel, 2019). In addition to recognizing letters visually, grade-one students practice forming letters correctly through handwriting instruction, which helps reinforce letter recognition skills (Graham et al., 2021). Proficient letter recognition leads to fluency in identifying letters quickly and accurately, which supports reading fluency and comprehension (Juel, 2020). Effective instructional strategies for developing letter recognition skills in grade-one students include explicit instruction, multisensory activities, letter games, and frequent practice opportunities (National Institute for Literacy, 2021). Late afternoon programs can play a crucial role in supporting the educational development of Grade-one students by providing opportunities for enrichment, socialization, and reinforcement of academic concepts. Late afternoon programs offer numerous advantages for students, fami-

lies, and communities. Late afternoon programs provide structured time for students to complete homework assignments, receive tutoring, and engage in academic enrichment activities, leading to improved academic performance (Durlak et al., 2020). Late afternoon programs often provide opportunities for students to develop a wide range of skills, including leadership, teamwork, communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking skills, which are essential for success in school and beyond (Eccles Gootman, 2021; Mahoney et al., 2019). Participation in after-school programs has been linked to a decreased likelihood of engaging in risky behaviors such as substance abuse, delinquency, and violence among adolescents (Mahoney et al., 2019; Vandell et al., 2021). Moreover, the Late afternoon Program and letter Recognition skills in Grade one was fundamental skills in early literacy development and are closely linked to reading success (Ehri, 2019). Research by Piasta and Wagner (2020) found that Grade-One students' letter recognition skills predict later reading abilities. Moreover, a study by McBride-Chang et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of early letter recognition proficiency in facilitating word reading and comprehension skills. Adams (2023) also highlighted the significance of systematic and explicit instruction in letter recognition for young learners, suggesting that targeted interventions can effectively enhance this skill. Late afternoon programs offer several advantages for grade one students, enhancing their overall development and academic success. Late afternoon programs provide additional time for academic reinforcement, homework assistance, and targeted instruction in foundational skills such as reading, writing, and mathematics. This extra support can help grade one student solidify their understanding of key concepts and improve their academic performance (Vandell et al., 2021). Grade one students can benefit from literacy-focused activities in late afternoon programs, such as reading aloud, phonics instruc-

tion, and guided reading sessions. These activities help strengthen letter recognition, phonemic awareness, and early reading comprehension skills, setting a solid foundation for future literacy development (Pianta et al., 2019). Late afternoon programs allow grade one students to interact with peers outside of the regular school day. Engaging in group activities, cooperative games, and team projects fosters social skills, cooperation, and friendship building, contributing to overall social development (Mahoney et al., 2019). Late afternoon programs often offer enrichment activities in art, music, science, and physical education. These activities allow grade one students to explore their interests, develop creativity, and build skills beyond the core academic curriculum (Beets et al., 2020). Late afternoon programs provide a safe and supervised environment for grade one students during the after-school hours. This structured setting offers continuity of care and ensures that students are engaged in productive and enriching activities, reducing the risk of unsupervised time or exposure to unsafe environments (Mahoney et al., 2019). Late afternoon programs play a vital role in supporting the holistic development of students by providing academic enrichment, socialization opportunities, and a safe environment during non-school hours. Late afternoon programs offer additional time for academic reinforcement, homework help, and enrichment activities, which can lead to improved academic performance and increased mastery of key concepts (Vandell et al., 2021). Late afternoon programs offer numerous benefits, they may also present some disadvantages for grade one students. Grade one students may already be fatigued after a full day of school, and attending a late afternoon program could further contribute to feelings of tiredness and overwhelm, potentially impacting their ability to engage effectively in activities (Matsuura, 2019). Late afternoon programs may result in less time for grade one students to spend with their families, limiting opportunities for bonding, relaxation, and family activities (Hofferth Sandberg, 2021). A late afternoon program may reduce grade one students' time for free play and unstructured activities, which are essential for creativity, imagination, and social development (Pellegrini Smith, 2021). Additional academic or extracurricular commitments through a late afternoon program may add to grade one students' stress levels and feelings of pressure, particularly if they already experience academic or social challenges during the school day (West et al., 2020). Late afternoon programs can pose logistical challenges for families, including arranging transportation to and from the program, coordinating schedules with work or other commitments, and managing additional expenses (Baker et al., 2019). Grade-one students' Letter recognition skills offer several advantages fundamental to their overall literacy development and academic success. Letter recognition skills serve as the building blocks for reading and writing. When students can identify letters accurately, they can begin to decode words and understand written language, laying the foundation for literacy (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). Letter recognition skills are closely tied to phonemic awareness, the ability to identify and manipulate individual sounds in spoken language. As students learn to recognize letters and associate them with their corresponding sounds, they develop phonemic awareness, essential for reading and spelling (National Reading Panel, 2019). As grade-one students become proficient in recognizing letters, they can expand their vocabulary by learning new words and understanding their meanings. This vocabulary development is critical for comprehension and communication (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). Letter recognition skills improve reading fluency, allowing students to read with incredible speed, accuracy, and expression. When students can quickly identify and decode letters, they can focus more on understanding the text and less on

decoding individual words (Juel, 2020). Letter recognition skills are essential for developing early writing skills. Once students can identify letters, they can begin to form them in writing and understand how letters represent sounds in words. This understanding lays the groundwork for spelling and composition (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). Mastering letter recognition skills boosts students' confidence in their ability to engage with written language. As students experience success in identifying letters, they become more motivated to continue learning and exploring literacy (Juel, 2020). Overall, letter recognition skills are crucial for grade-one students as they embark on their journey toward becoming proficient readers and writers. By developing strong letter recognition skills, students gain the essential tools they need to succeed academically and beyond. Letter recognition skills are crucial for grade-one students' literacy development, but there are some potential disadvantages or challenges associated. Excessive emphasis on letter recognition skills alone may lead to a narrow focus on isolated literacy components, potentially neglecting other essential aspects of literacy development such as comprehension, vocabulary, and fluency (Pinnell et al., 1995). Grade-one students may struggle to transfer their letter recognition skills to meaningful reading and writing contexts if instruction does not integrate them into authentic literacy activities and experiences (Snow et al., 2021). Moreover, some grade-one students may experience frustration or anxiety if they struggle with letter recognition skills, especially if they feel pressure to perform academically or compare themselves to their peers (Pettigrew Reppa, 2019). Rote memorization of letters without understanding their phonetic or semantic properties may limit students' ability to apply letter recognition skills flexibly in different contexts or when encountering unfamiliar words (Ehri et al., 2019). Grade-one students who struggle with letter recognition skills may be labeled as "behind" or "at-risk," leading to feelings of inadequacy or stigma that could affect their self-esteem and motivation (Ehri et al., 2019). Some grade-one students may not be developmentally ready to master letter recognition skills, particularly if they have limited exposure to literacy-rich environments or if their cognitive or linguistic development varies widely (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). In addition, some grade-one students may not be developmentally ready to master letter recognition skills, particularly if they have limited exposure to literacy-rich environments or if their cognitive or linguistic development varies widely (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). It's important for educators to be aware of these potential disadvantages and address them through balanced literacy instruction that integrates letter recognition skills with meaningful reading, writing, and language experiences. Letter recognition skills are critical for grade-one students as they lay the foundation for literacy development and academic success. Letter recognition skills are the gateway to reading. Grade-one students must be able to identify and differentiate between letters of the alphabet to begin decoding words and understanding written language (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). Letter recognition skills are closely linked to phonemic awareness, which is the ability to hear, identify, and manipulate individual sounds in spoken language. Understanding letters and their corresponding sounds is essential for developing phonemic awareness, which is a foundational skill for reading and spelling (National Reading Panel, 2019). Letter recognition skills facilitate vocabulary expansion by enabling students to learn new words and understand their meanings. As grade-one students become proficient in recognizing letters, they can begin to associate letters with sounds and use this knowledge to decode words and expand their vocabulary (National Early Literacy Panel, 2022). Letter recognition skills are essential for writing development. Grade-one

students must be able to identify and write letters accurately to compose written text, spell words correctly, and communicate effectively through writing (Puranik Lonigan, 2019). Proficient letter recognition skills contribute to positive reading experiences for grade-one students. When students can easily recognize letters and decode words, they are more likely to experience success and enjoyment in reading, fostering a lifelong love of literacy (Adams, 2023).

In summary, letter recognition skills are crucial for grade-one students as they provide the foundation for reading, phonemic awareness development, early literacy achievement, vocabulary expansion, writing development, and positive reading experiences. By mastering letter recognition skills, grade-one students gain essential tools for academic success and lifelong learning.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we will outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study. This will encompass selecting the study's design, identifying the respondents and the sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher employed artificial intelligence methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation. Artificial Intelligence (AI) was expressly utilized to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is being openly communicated to adhere to ethical norms in research. Leveraging AI for proofreading underscores a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledges AI's growing role and potential in professional and academic writing.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design is good when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the study subjects were an intact group of learners.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects were 60 grade one learners, of whom 28 were from section A, the controlled group, and 32 were from section B, the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study used a non-random assignment of subjects, where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

2.3. Data instruments—In this study, the researcher designed a pretest and posttest to gauge the letter recognition skills of grade one learners. The test questions were based on the competencies of grade one pupils and were validated by experts. Both the pre- and post-performance tests consisted of a 25-item test to evaluate the academic performance of the research subjects. The pretest was conducted prior to the treatment to assess the letter recognition skills, while the posttest was administered to measure the treatment's impact. To assess the letter recognition skills of grade one learners, a continuum based on the DepEd rating system was employed.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—The data-gathering process will begin with the researcher drafting a letter to request permission to conduct the research study. These letters will be sent to Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V, the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division

of Davao Del Sur, and to the relevant school principal. Following the distribution of the permission letters to the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent and the principal of Almendras Elementary School, the researcher will proceed to create a questionnaire and seek validation from experts experienced in the relevant field of study. The study will be conducted at Almendras Elementary School after obtaining permission. The research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by expert validators. The researcher will administer a pretest to both the controlled and experimental classes and then commence the experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer a posttest to both sec-

tions. The subjects' scores will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation, after which the researcher will analyze and interpret the gathered data.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study will utilize the following statistical tools: Mean: used to describe the letter recognition skills of the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pretest and posttest. t-test for uncorrelated samples: to determine the significance of the difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores in the experimental and controlled groups. Eta square: to gauge the magnitude of the effect of the late Afternoon Program on the letter recognition skills of grade one learners.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses the problems in this study. They are thoroughly discussed, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners, and the Significant Relationship between the Pre-test and post-test scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade seven learners. The control group got a mean of 58.08 or begin-

ning, while the experimental group got a mean of 61.24 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	28	14.51	58.08	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	32	15.31	61.24	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during the pre-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group, although both belong to the Beginning level. This finding is congruent with the idea of the National Early Literacy Panel (2022), which cited that letter recognition skills in grade-one learners offer several advantages that are fundamental to their overall literacy development and academic suc-

cess. Letter recognition skills serve as the building blocks for reading and writing. When students can identify letters accurately, they can begin to decode words and understand written language, laying the foundation for literacy. Late afternoon programs offer several advantages for grade one learners, enhancing their overall development and academic success. Late afternoon programs provide additional time for

academic reinforcement, homework assistance, and targeted instruction in foundational skills such as reading, writing, and mathematics. This extra support can help grade one learner solidify their understanding of key concepts and improve their academic performance (Vandell et

al., 2021). Post-Test Score of Learners Table 2 shows the post-test scores of the grade seven learners. The controlled group got the mean of 20.48, or Developing, while the experimental group gained the mean of 21.53, or Approaching Proficiency.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Post-test	28	20.48	81.92	Developing
Experimental Group				
Post-test	32	21.53	86.12	Approaching Proficiency

It can be gleaned from the table that during the post-test, the experimental group had a higher mean rating than the control group. It got a mean rating increase of 6.22 from a mean rating of 15.31 to 21.53. This means that the experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent with the idea of the National Early Literacy Panel (2022), which cited that as grade-one students become proficient in recognizing letters, they can expand their vocabulary by learning new words and understanding their meanings. This vocabulary development is critical for comprehension and communication. Letter recognition skills contribute to improved reading fluency, allowing students to read with greater speed, accuracy, and expression. When students can quickly identify and decode letters, they can focus more on understanding the text and less on decoding individual words (Juel, 2020). Late afternoon Program

and Letter Recognition Skills of Grade One are fundamental skills in early literacy development and are closely linked to reading success (Ehri, 2019). Research by Piasta and Wagner (2020) found that letter recognition skills in Grade-One learners are predictive of later reading abilities. Moreover, a study by McBride-Chang et al. (2021) emphasized the importance of early letter recognition proficiency in facilitating word reading and comprehension skills. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Table 3 shows the test for the significant difference between the pretest and post-test scores of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.43 with a p-value of .0331, which is less than the .05 level of significance. This means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post-test scores of the grade one learners.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	21	-5.43	.0331	Significant

This implies that the used of late afternoon program have contributed to the letter recognition skills which is revealed by the scores of the grade one learners. This finding is in line with the statement of Adams (2023) who said that Proficient letter recognition skills contribute to positive reading experiences for grade-one learners. When students can easily recognize letters and decode words, they are more likely to experience success and enjoyment in reading, fostering a lifelong love of literacy. Grade one pupils can benefit from literacy-focused activities in late afternoon programs, such as reading

aloud, phonics instruction, and guided reading sessions. These activities help strengthen letter recognition, phonemic awareness, and early reading comprehension skills, setting a strong foundation for future literacy development (Pianta et al., 2019). Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade one learners Table 4 highlights the late afternoon program’s test of the letter recognition skills of Grade One learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.451, which signifies a large effect.

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pre-test and Post-test Scores of the Grade One Learners

N	t-value	Eta²	Descriptive Value	Decision
60	-4.36	0.451	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

This implies that teachers should look for a strategy to enhance students’ letter recognition skills for Grade One learners. Developing letter recognition skills in grade one learners is a critical step in their literacy journey. It lays the foundation for reading and writing, supports cognitive development, enhances language and communication skills, and boosts confidence and motivation. Late afternoon programs play a

vital role in supporting the holistic development of students by providing academic enrichment, socialization opportunities, and a safe environment during non-school hours. Late afternoon programs offer additional time for academic reinforcement, homework help, and enrichment activities, which can lead to improved academic performance and increased mastery of key concepts (Vandell et al., 2021).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter summarizes the findings, conclusions, and recommendations drawn by the researcher after analyzing and interpreting the findings. This study sought to determine the effect of the late afternoon program on the letter recognition skills of grade one learners. This study used a quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. A non-equivalent design is good when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the study subjects were intact learners. This study was conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade one learners – 32 were from section A, which comprised the controlled group, and 28 were from section B, which is the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous; therefore, pupils of sections A and B have identical ranges of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This

study revealed that the utilization of the late afternoon program has increased the letter recognition skills of grade one learners. It also revealed that there is a magnitude of difference between the post-test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade one learners in both the controlled and experimental groups were at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group were at the Developing level, while the post-test scores of the experimental group were at the Approaching Proficiency level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade one learners use a late afternoon program to further develop their letter recognition skills and foster an environment conducive to early literacy development. By implementing teaching strategies that ensure that all students can develop strong letter recognition skills, teachers can help young learners embark on a rewarding journey of reading and writing, setting the stage for future literacy success. The school heads should promote the use of the later afternoon program as a strategy that would enhance the letter recognition skills of grade one learners. The study revealed that it is effective, especially on subjects considered vital in developing fundamental skills for early literacy, serving as the gateway to reading and writing proficiency. A school policy about the utilization of late afternoon programs can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teaching during LAC sessions using late afternoon programs as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of the late afternoon program as a teaching strategy be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

5. References

- Adams, M. J. (1990). *Beginning to read: Thinking and learning about print*. MIT Press.
- Afterschool Alliance. (2017). Investing in our children: A plan to expand access to afterschool and summer opportunities for middle school students.
- Baker, M., Gruber, J., & Milligan, K. (2008). Universal child care, maternal labor supply, and family well-being. *Journal of Political Economy*, 116(4), 709–745.
- Beets, M. W., Beighle, A., Erwin, H. E., & Huberty, J. L. (2009). After-school program impact on physical activity and fitness: A meta-analysis. *American Journal of Preventive Medicine*, 36(6), 527–537.
- Ehri, L. C., Nunes, S. R., Stahl, S. A., & Willows, D. M. (2001). Systematic phonics instruction helps students learn to read: Evidence from the national reading panel's meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 71(3), 393–447.
- Graham, S., Harris, K. R., & Fink-Chorzempa, B. (2008). Primary grade teachers' instructional adaptations for struggling writers: A national survey. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 100(4), 907–919.
- Hofferth, S. L., & Sandberg, J. F. (2001). How american children spend their time. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 63(2), 295–308.
- Juel, C. (1988). Learning to read and write: A longitudinal study of 54 children from first through fourth grades. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 80(4), 437–447.

- Mahoney, J. L., Vandell, D. L., Simpkins, S., & Zarrett, N. (2009). Adolescent out-of-school activities. In *Handbook of adolescent psychology* (pp. 228–267, Vol. 2). John Wiley Sons.
- Matsuura, R. (2009). The effects of extended school time on students' academic achievement: Evidence from a natural experiment in Japan. *Economics of Education Review*, 28(3), 295–311.
- National Early Literacy Panel. (2008). *Developing early literacy: Report of the national early literacy panel*. National Institute for Literacy.
- National Reading Panel. (2000). *Teaching children to read: An evidence-based assessment of the scientific research literature on reading and its implications for reading instruction*. National Institute of Child Health; Human Development.
- Pellegrini, A. D., & Smith, P. K. (1998). Physical activity play: The nature and function of a neglected aspect of play. *Child Development*, 69(3), 577–598.
- Pettigrew, J., & Reppa, I. (2019). Addressing anxiety and perfectionism in young learners: A case study on early reading intervention. *Early Child Development and Care*, 189(7), 1204–1218.
- Pianta, R. C., Barnett, W. S., Burchinal, M., & Thornburg, K. R. (2009). The effects of preschool education: What we know, how public policy is or is not aligned with the evidence base, and what we need to know. *Psychological Science in the Public Interest*, 10(2), 49–88.
- Pinnell, G. S., Pikulski, J. J., Wixson, K. K., Campbell, J. R., Gough, P. B., & Beatty, A. S. (1995). *Listening to children read aloud*. U.S. Department of Education, Office of Educational Research; Improvement, National Institute on Student Achievement, Curriculum, Assessment.
- Puranik, C. S., & Lonigan, C. J. (2011). Alphabet knowledge and early writing skills in preschool children. *Reading and Writing*, 24(2), 173–189.
- Snow, C. E., Burns, M. S., & Griffin, P. (1998). *Preventing reading difficulties in young children*. National Academies Press.
- Vandell, D. L., Reiser, E. R., & Pierce, K. M. (2007). Out-of-school settings as a developmental context for children and youth. *Advances in child development and behavior*, 35, 59–105.
- West, M. R., Kraft, M. A., Finn, A. S., Martin, R. E., Duckworth, A. L., & Gabrieli, C. F. O. (2016). Promise and paradox: Measuring students' non-cognitive skills and the impact of schooling. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 38(1), 148–170.